

Abyssal turbulence in the vicinity of Lucky Strike

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Summary

Hydrothermal vents are places with a high turbulent activity that originates from the interaction of deep ocean currents with the Mid Ocean Ridge (MOR) bathymetry, but as well by the presence of turbulent plume from hydrothermal vent fields located in the MOR. This work is split into two parts, the first part consists of an exploration of observations from nine years of mooring deployments near the Lucky Strike hydrothermal vent field. We computed power spectra estimates to determine the characteristic processes happening at this location and we found that the motions were dominated by the internal tides and we found no particular features indicating interannual variability in the data. The second part consisted of performing an LES simulation of a buoyant plume and developing an energy framework in an open volume to study the pathways in which the mechanical energy is transformed into this system. Using this framework, we were able to estimate a mixing efficiency of the plume of ~ 0.7 .

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1 Introduction

The deep ocean is the least explored place on Earth and possibly in the closest vicinity of our solar system. The massive expanse of the ocean and challenging conditions in its deepest parts create an extreme environment in which our exploration capacity is bounded by the current technological advances. Historically, the lack of knowledge of the deep ocean created misconceptions about the shape of the seafloor, how the ocean flowed in its deepest regions, and the fauna found at its deepest regions. Although, during the last century, many discoveries challenged these ideas and revolutionize completely the field of oceanography.

In particular, the revolution began in 1959 when Marie Tharp and [Heezen et al. \(1959\)](#) published the first global map of the ocean floor, in which they discovered the existence of the Mid Ocean Ridges (MOR). This discovery was a paradigm shift in geology because it was conclusive evidence that confirmed the plate tectonics hypothesis ([Kunzig, 2000](#)). Around the same time, more evidence came to light of the existence of deep water currents that provided cold and oxygen-rich water to all the ocean basins ([Stommel, 1958](#)). In two seminal articles, [Stommel and Arons \(1959a,b\)](#) proposed a hypothesis that explained the mechanisms of deep water formation and distribution of the oceans basins, by predicting the existence of the Meridional Overturning Circulation (MOC). Their work launched several expeditions to measure those features in which new technologies were developed, such as the Swallow floats build by [Swallow \(1955\)](#). Throughout these oceanographic campaigns, they were able to detect some of the features of the MOC and also demonstrated that the deep ocean circulation was turbulent, something that contradicted the idea of a motionless ocean.

One of the biggest discoveries in deep ocean science came in 1977, with the discovery of hydrothermal vents. Previous to that year, oceanographers collected evidence of possible hydrothermal activity in the seafloor, such as measurements of basins in the Red Sea filled with warm and salty water that contrasted with the near-freezing deep water temperatures ([Degens and Ross, 1969](#)), and the detection of plumes of water containing an excess of Helium-3 in the Galapagos Rise, which could only come from the interaction between the lithosphere and the ocean water ([Clarke et al., 1969](#)). By 1977 an American expedition was launched to explore the Galapagos Rise in search

of the suspected hot springs. In an article, the leader of the expedition [Ballard \(1977\)](#) mentions that when they localized the vents and dived to that spot, they were astonished to find otherworldly ecosystems full of life, that defied our understanding of life itself. It demonstrated that complex and diverse ecosystems could exist in the deep ocean, out of the reach of sunlight.

Deep in the ocean, immense knowledge voids remain waiting to be explored. These rich environments face the rampant destruction caused by human activity, threatening to disappear before we fully understand them. Therefore, there is an urgency to explore these knowledge voids in which each deep-sea immersion and instrument deployment has a great potential to advance our understanding of deep ocean environments. In particular, hydrothermal vents are threatened by deep-sea mining due to the large deposits of rare minerals around the vents. While we just began to explore them, many questions about their importance for the ocean remain open, such as their contribution to ocean circulation, the transport of nutrients, and many more.

1.1 Hydrothermal vents

Hydrothermal vents are conduits of hot water charged with chemicals that circulate from the lithosphere to the hydrosphere ([Di Iorio et al., 2012](#)). This circulation is known as hydrothermal circulation and it occurs when water penetrates through cracks in the ocean floor along volcanically active areas such as the MORs. When the water filtrates through the cracks, the rock heats and chemically modify the water as it descends. The water can reach a temperature of around 20 °C to 400 °C, and as it is heated it becomes extremely buoyant, rising rapidly back to the seafloor until it is released to the ocean water column in form of plumes ([German and Von Damm, 2006](#)).

The vent discharge has a wide range of temperature and chemical composition that depends on the location and the type of activity found in the corresponding spreading center. More commonly, the vents are classified by the exit temperature of the vents, particularly they are classified into two types: high-temperature vents and low-temperature diffuse vents.

In the high-temperature vents, we find black and white smokers. Particularly, black smokers are the most spectacular vents that exist. They are characterized for emanating from tall chimneys that can reach heights of more than 20 m, with an internal diameter on the order of 10 cm. They have the particularity that the discharged fluid can reach temperatures over 400 °C and appears to be black smoke because the iron-sulfide reacts and precipitates when it comes into contact with the surrounding water ([German and Von Damm, 2006](#)). On the other hand, the low-temperature diffuse vents occur, when the cold seawater and the geothermally heated water mixes within the subsurface. These

sources have a typical temperature of tens of degrees Celsius, with vertical exit speed of tens of centimeters per second. The plumes from these vents, also known as lazy plumes, rise only a few meters above the source, but can be entrained by high-temperature vents (Di Iorio et al., 2012).

Hydrothermal vent sites are a mixture of the different types of vents, and the source fluxes vary greatly from one vent to another. Even by being part of the same vent system, you could find a black smoker with a temperature discharge of around 300 °C siting 100 m apart from a diffuse system expelling water at 30 °C. The discharge depends in its totality from the volcanic activity in which these systems sit on. This aspect, combined by the diversity of vents, makes difficult to measure the heat flux of an entire vent field, therefore, Oceanographers use other techniques to estimate the heat flux associated with the vents, such as buoyant plume models.

1.2 Lucky Strike - study location

Lucky Strike is a vent field or system that was discovered by chance by the French-American Ridge Atlantic (FARA) program in 1992. During that expedition, a dredge brought on deck sulfide deposits covered with living organisms, characteristic of hydrothermal vent fields, indicating the possible existence of a vent field in that position. This discovery was confirmed later in 1993, with several immersions done with *Alvin* the submersible. The name Lucky Strike is due to this fortuitous discovery (Langmuir et al., 1997).

The vent field is located in the Mid Atlantic Ridge (MAR) between 37°3'N and 37°37'N, 400 km southwest of the Azores Islands, and the Azores Triple Junction (see Figure 1.1). The rift valley where the vent field is located is known as the Lucky Strike Segment. This segment is 60 km long and 10 km to 15 km wide, bounded by 1000 m high axial valley walls. At its center, the segment shallows (~1700 m deep) due to the presence of the Lucky Strike volcano (Ondréas et al., 2009).

Lucky Strike is one of the largest axial volcano within the rift valley on the MAR (see Figure 1.1) and hosts the highest diversity of species of all the vent systems in slow-spreading ridges. At its center, in the caldera¹, there is a young solidified lava lake about 200 m wide, which is the place that has hydrothermal activity. In Lucky Strike there are 30 vents sites distributed over a 1 km² area (Karson et al., 2015). The plume has an estimated height of ~100 m, with a total heat flux of (3800 ± 1200) MW (Jean-Baptiste et al., 2008).

¹It actually is a depression found between three extinct volcanoes and not an actual caldera from a volcano. We mention caldera several times in this work, but we actually mean the depression.

Figure 1.1: At the right, the bathymetry of the Lucky Strike segment placed at the Southwest of the Azores triple junction in the MAR. The Red square represents the location of the Lucky Strike volcano. On the right, the bathymetry of the Lucky Strike volcano with its crater at the centre, surrounded by three peaks.

1.3 Monitoring the Mid-Atlantic Ridge project

The Monitoring the Mid-Atlantic Ridge (MoMAR) project is a long-term multidisciplinary program created by the international InterRidge program in 1998, to study hydrothermal vents in the MAR (Colaço et al., 2011). As part of this project, in 2010 the EMSO-Azores marine observatory² was deployed in the Lucky Strike volcano, devoted to the study of Mid-Ocean ridge processes, from the seafloor to the water column. The project has three main objectives: (i) to study the hydrothermal fluxes to the ocean at its relation with the seismicity and volcanic activity; (ii) study the impact of telluric, climatic, and anthropogenic changes of the local ecosystem and hydrothermal communities; (iii) and to study the ocean dynamics in the steep axial valley topography and its impact on the dispersion of hydrothermal discharge.

The observatory is maintained every year during the MoMARSAT cruises, in which part of the instruments are recovered, serviced on board and redeployed, following the new objectives set for the next mission for the year to come. In particular, since the first deployment of the observatory, a mooring was placed Southeast of the Lucky Strike

²This project is part of the European Multidisciplinary Seafloor Observation (EMSO) initiative. It is part of the European Sea Observatory NETwork (ESONET) <http://www.esonet-noe.org/>.

volcano and since then the mooring is serviced every year and deployed in the same region as the first one, although not in the exact location because the mooring is deployed from the surface, and it can drift horizontally while making its descent to the seafloor.

1.4 Objectives of this study

This work is divided into two separate parts. The first part consists of analyzing observations from the mooring anchored to the South-West of the Lucky Strike volcano. The objective is to identify the different processes that occur over Lucky Strike, such as internal tides or passing mesoscale eddies. Also, the 9 years of data collected for the mooring allow us to see if there is interannual variability in this region.

The second part of the work consisted in performing an idealized numerical simulation of a plume. The objective of this experiment is to study the mechanical energy budget of a plume in a stratified environment, to study the pathways in which the mechanical energy in the flow is transformed, focusing in how the potential energy is transformed into kinetic energy, as well as estimating the mixing efficiency of the plume, based on this framework.

2 Plume theory

2.1 Plume dynamics

Vent discharges form turbulent buoyant plumes as they ascend the water column. These plumes entrain cold surrounding water as they rise, diluting the plume continuously with ambient fluid. If the plume is in a homogeneous environment, the plume will ascent indefinitely or until it reaches the surface. However, in a stratified environment, the rising plumes will decrease their density, until they reach an equilibrium level in which the plume will stop rising and will start spreading laterally (Lupton, 1995). Plumes occur in a wide range of scales in the ocean and the atmosphere, but in general, they are an important mechanism for the dispersal of chemicals and thermal fluxes, as well as they can disperse material.

There are a large number of theoretical models that describe the behavior of plumes. One of the most widely used models is the MTT model, from Morton et al. (1956). They derived a set of equations for the conservation of volume flux, momentum flux, and buoyancy flux for a point source in a stratified environment. They introduced the entrainment hypothesis to close the equations, which consists in defining the mean horizontal velocity proportional to the mean vertical velocity at a certain height. These equations allow us to determine the height and the shape of the plume, based on the buoyancy flux and the ambient stratification. The MTT has proven to be very effective in modeling turbulent plumes in stratified environments, and there have been modifications to the model, by adding the effects of rotation (Speer and Marshall, 1995), or by modeling non-point sources. These models are used to estimate the heat fluxes from hydrothermal vents, by measuring the plume height and the local stratification (Woods, 2010).

Despite the robustness and modifications of the MMT model, there are certain areas in which the model underperforms, such as when describing lazy plumes and plumes with low Froude numbers (Kaye, 2008), which highlight the importance investigating new approaches to model buoyant plumes. Following this idea, Devenish et al. (2010) compared a Large Eddy Simulation (LES) of a buoyant plume with the MTT model, in which they computed the entrainment constant and the shape of the plume in a stably stratified environment and in a uniform environment. They found that the LES results

agree with MTT theory in the unstratified case, and for the stratified case, the results also agree with MTT for the region below the neutral buoyancy level. Above it, the LES accounts for the processes happening at the top of the plume, such as the overturning and the entrainment happening at this level. Based on this result and the success of the LES model to simulate turbulent plumes, we decided to use an LES code to simulate a plume, but with our focus on studying how energy is processed by the plume, instead of doing a comparison with the reference models.

2.2 Energetic framework

To study the pathways for energy conversion in a particular flow or experiment it is useful to think of our experiment as a system that processes energy. In this system, energy is injected, then is converted or dissipated, and lastly is expelled from the system. The way this occurs depends of the type of system that we are analysing, and therefore the energetic framework is exclusive of the type of flow and it is derived from the equations of motions that describe it.

The core of this framework relies in splitting the potential energy into available potential energy (E_a or sometimes referred as APE) and background potential energy (E_b). In particular, E_a is defined as the potential energy that is available for conversion into kinetic energy (Lorenz, 1955). The E_b is the remainder of the potential energy that cannot create motion but it can exchange energy with other forms (Hughes et al., 2013). In essence, the energy budget can be viewed as the interaction between three energy reservoirs: E_b , E_a , and the kinetic energy reservoir (K). The interactions are the energy fluxes that convert energy from one reservoir to another, or eventually that inject or dissipate energy from the system. This framework has proven to be useful to compute the mixing efficiency of the flow.

There are studies where this energetic framework was used in idealized experiments, for example: Winters et al. (1995) developed and used the framework to study the mixing efficiency of a Kelvin-Helmholtz instability, Hughes et al. (2009) also used this framework to explore the energy flux that maintains the overturning circulation in the ocean; and Hughes et al. (2013) used this framework to analyse the mechanical energy for a Rayleigh-Bernard convection in a closed volume. We based large part of our analysis in the latter study, with the only major modification that our analysis uses an open control volume instead of a closed one.

Figure 2.1: Schematic of the mechanical energetic framework for the plume in an open control volume. K is the kinetic energy reservoir, E_a is the APE reservoir, and E_b is the background potential energy reservoir. ϕ_e is the input of mechanical energy, ϕ_b is the APE generation from the E_b , ϕ_z is the flux from E_a to kinetic energy, ϵ_a is the diapycnal dissipation, and ϵ_k is the dissipation of kinetic energy.

2.3 Mechanical energy budget of a buoyant plume

Following the analysis done by [Hughes et al. \(2013\)](#), but considering an open system instead of a closed one, we defined the framework in which the energy reservoirs interact. The system consists of a control volume that contains the plume, in which the plume occupies a small fraction of it. The outside of the control volume is considered to be a thermal reservoir, with a background stratification $b_r(z)$. The reservoir is considered large enough so that the plume doesn't alter the background stratification. When the plume is in a steady state with the environment, there is a thermal balance between the heat entering the control volume by the bottom forcing and the heat exchanged with the reservoir.

The schematic in [Figure 2.1](#) summarises the energy framework for the plume system. The control volume is an open system where energy is introduced in the E_b reservoir through the flux ϕ_e , and energy is extracted from the K reservoir by the terms ϕ_p and ϵ_k .

The input of the mechanical energy in system is denoted as ϕ_e and it is composed of three processes that are described in [Figure 2.2](#). The main idea is that when the plume is in a stable state, water gets sucked into the plume close to the bottom, at height z_0 with a certain buoyancy b_0 and pressure, then it gets carried up by the plume and is expelled at a height z_1 with a buoyancy b_1 and a different pressure. This process injects background potential energy to the system by lifting parcels of water. The pressure work also has a role moving these parcels, as well as the heat flux converted into buoyancy flux Q_b , injected at the bottom. Following this scheme, we can say that ϕ_e is the sum of three terms

$$\phi_e = \phi(b_1 z_1 - b_0 z_0) - Q_b S_{\text{bot}} z_0 + \phi(p_r(z_1) - p_r(z_0)), \quad (2.1)$$

where the first term is the flux of background potential energy integrated over the lateral

Figure 2.2: Schematic of the plume system seeing a factory. Q_b is the buoyancy forcing imposed at the bottom, ϕ denotes the fluxes that carry in and out potential energy to the system, \overline{wp}^S is the energy flux irradiated as internal waves, z_0 and z_1 are reference heights.

surface of the control volume accounting for the water going in and out of the system; the second term is the source of potential energy imposed at the bottom by the buoyancy flux Q_b ; and the third term is the pressure work associated with the fact that the inflow and the out flow don't occur at the same pressure level. The term $p_r(z) = -\int_0^z b_r(z') dz'$ is the hydrostatic pressure in the thermal reservoir.

The equations that describe the energy interaction between reservoirs are derived from the Boussinesq equations used by the model, the derivation can be found in the Appendix A.1. These equations are:

$$\partial_t K = \phi_z - \phi_p - \epsilon_k, \quad (2.2a)$$

$$\partial_t E_a = -\phi_z + \phi_b - \epsilon_a, \quad (2.2b)$$

$$\partial_t E_b = -\phi_b + \phi_e + \epsilon_a, \quad (2.2c)$$

where $\phi_z = \overline{(b - b_r)w}^V$ is the volume integrated conversion from potential to kinetic energy (V denotes volume integrated), $\phi_b = \overline{Q(b - b_r)}^V / N^2$ is the volume integrated APE generation term from the background potential energy due to the thermal forcing integrated over the volume, ϵ_k is the dissipation of kinetic energy due to the viscous stress, ϵ_a is the dissipation of available potential energy due to the molecular diffusion and equivalently the diapycnal mixing rate (Winters et al., 1995), and ϕ_e is the input of potential energy associated with the forcing already described, and $\phi_p = \overline{wp}^S$ is surface integrated kinetic energy flux radiated into the internal wave field on the top surface of the control volume (S denotes surface integrated), schematized as the wiggly arrows at

the top of Figure 2.2.

2.4 Mixing efficiency

The mixing efficiency is the proportion of kinetic energy lost by the fluid that leads to mixing (Peltier and Caulfield, 2003). In the control volume it is defined as

$$\mathcal{E} = \frac{\epsilon_a}{\epsilon_k + \epsilon_a}. \quad (2.3)$$

Assuming a steady state, where $\partial_t K \approx 0$ and $\partial_t E_a \approx 0$, and by using the equations 2.2, we can redefine the mixing efficiency as

$$\mathcal{E} = \frac{\phi_b - \phi_z}{\phi_b + \phi_p}. \quad (2.4)$$

This equation allow us to compute the mixing efficiency in a numerical simulation of a plume in its steady state, by computing the fluxes ϕ_b, ϕ_z and ϕ_p , which are the principal mechanical energy pathways in the plume system.

3 Methodology

3.1 Mooring and observations

Moorings are a recurrent sampling method used by oceanographers to measure the ocean's properties for long periods of time in a fixed point in space. It consists of a line that connects different type of instruments and is anchored to the seafloor. Many projects charged of monitoring variations in long time scales install their instruments in moorings in strategic points. In particular, the mooring used in the MoMAR project give us the opportunity to observe a record of 9 years over an hydrothermal vent field.

The mooring used in this project is composed of three types of instruments: the *RBR TR-1060* and *RBR TR-1050* temperature recorders (referred as RBR), the *SBE 37-SM MicroCAT* conductivity-temperature-pressure recorder (referred as SBE), and the *Nortek AquaDopp* single-point horizontal current metre (referred as AquaDopp). The RBRs have a sampling period of 3 min and it is the instrument that is predominant in the mooring, spanning from the top of the mooring down to the seafloor. The SBE is a fixed CTD. It was placed with constancy at -1000 m and -1700 m with some years in which a third SBE was placed at -1300 m, and it has a sampling period of 6 min. The AquaDopp has a sampling frequency of 6 min and measures the horizontal components of the velocity of the flow, it was placed 10 metres above the seafloor, except for 2013 when no AquaDopp was placed.

The vertical position of the instruments in the mooring changed every year. In the left panel in Figure 3.1 is possible to see the different vertical configurations of the mooring throughout the 9 years of the campaign. The uneven floor of the mooring site makes it difficult to keep the same type of instruments at the same pressure level for all years. The bottom depth of the mooring was estimated by using the bottom pressure gauge in the SBE located at the bottom and by knowing the estimated location at which the mooring was released. In the right panel in Figure 3.1, the mooring locations are shown highlighting that they have been placed consistently at the Southeast of the Lucky Strike volcano, partly because the instruments are not designed to be exposed to high temperatures and the corrosion of the plume, found closer to the caldera.

Figure 3.1: The mooring vertical and horizontal positions. The left panel shows the estimated real depth of all the instruments and the right panel shows the estimated location of the mooring, with respect to the Lucky Strike volcano. The pink stars indicate the position of the mooring each year.

3.2 Data analysis

The number of instruments installed each year in the mooring, combined with nine years of measurements, made the task of processing the data somehow overwhelming. Each instrument recorded its data in an independent file with a specific file format and some of these instruments had outliers or false measurements that had to be verified one by one before using them in a more in-depth analysis. This was the reason for deciding to compile the clean data by year and by instrument type in a NetCDF format. The NetCDF files are going to be published with an associated DOI as soon as all the publishing standards are met.

All the data analysis for the mooring was done in Python. The following subsections describe the methods used for this analysis.

3.2.1 Signal analysis

As part of the signal analysis, we estimated the power spectral density (PSD) of the signals recorded by the mooring's instruments. The PSD gives information on how the signal is distributed into different discrete frequencies, and therefore it can be used for identifying the different forcings acting at a precise depth in the water column. A Fast Fourier transform (FFT) is used to convert the signal from a time domain into a frequency domain. From the different existing methods used to estimate the PSD, we used the [Welch \(1967\)](#) method because it yields a clean PSD curve with a high resolution in a determined frequency region.

Welch's method consists of splitting a time series into segments of different sizes and perform a periodogram over those segments. The computed PSDs are averaged

Figure 3.2: The power spectral density from temperature measured with the SBE at 1000 m deep. The frequency is in counts per day (cpd). The colors highlight the different frequency regions for which a Welch PSD estimate with a specific segment size, except for the lowest frequency region in which a normal periodogram was used. The background curve in grey is a normal periodogram.

between them returning a mean PSD. The size of the segments is what determines the band in which the resolution will be high, i.e. when the segment size is small, the PSD for the high frequencies will be best represented, while the events that have a bigger characteristic time than the segment size will be poorly represented; and vice versa, large segments will increase the resolution for low frequencies but will return a noisy PSD in the high frequencies. To avoid having edge effects that could arise from splitting the series into segments, an overlap between segment is implemented as well as a Hann filter or Hanning window, in which the edges are smoothed, to remove the edge effects of performing the FFT.

We segmented the time series into different frequency regions to compute the PSD using the Welch method, to maximize the resolution in most of the frequency spectrum. The overlap between segments was of 15%. Figure 3.2 shows the segment sizes for the different frequency regions. The segments sizes and the frequency regions were selected arbitrarily by trial and error until we got a noise-free well-defined curve in the region of interest. In the low-frequency region that corresponds to more than 10 days, a normal periodogram was implemented which is equivalent to doing a Welch PSD estimate with a window of the same size as the total time length of the series.

For the analysis, we compared the spectral density estimates for instruments at similar depths, for all the years available, as well as a depth comparison between the same type of instruments, for each year. The variables used for the analysis were temperature, conductivity (to compute the density), and the speed from the current metre. We found that the spectral curves were similar between them, which led us to select a

representative year per analysis from which we build the discussion, leaving the rest of the plots in the Appendix A.2.

In particular, for power density spectral estimates of horizontal kinetic energy (computed with the speed measured by the Aquadopp), we took a similar approach as Ferrari and Wunsch (2009) did, and established a framework of qualitative separation by frequency (σ) bands. Also, we computed the scaling power laws of these bands using the least squares method.

3.2.2 Distributions

We computed the probability density function (PDF) for the temperature, speed, and direction, and compared them between different years at similar levels, giving an insight of possible yearly variations. To compute the PDF we used the kernel density estimation method, which consists of using Gaussian kernels to compute the PDF of a random variable. The comparison between years was particularly challenging because many instruments were not placed consistently at the same level during the different years, and these depth variations made it difficult to have a robust comparison. For the speed and direction, we used the AquaDopp placed near the seafloor for all years except 2013. And for the temperature, the SBEs were placed consistently at the same levels, making this the preferred instrument to compare.

3.3 Plume experiment

To complement the analysis of the turbulence surrounding the hydrothermal vents, we performed a 3D idealized simulation of a buoyant plume in a stratified medium.

When designing the experiment, we found that stratification was straightforward to implement in a simplified model, by setting adequate boundary conditions and an initial stratification profile. Also, it is straightforward to include rotation in the experiment, just by including the Coriolis term in the equations of motion, although in the analysis we found that the inclusion of the rotation term prevents of having a stable state in the plume, making difficult to implement the energy framework analysis. Other forcings like the internal tides are difficult to implement in an idealized model, so it was not considered for this experiment.

The objective of the experiment was to compute the energy budget of the plume, by computing the fluxes of energy between the mechanical energy reservoirs E_a , E_b and K . To achieve this objective, we developed a set of tools to diagnose these quantities by integrating the quantity of interest in a control volume or through this control volume. Also, these tools had to deal with the numerical technicalities associated with the model, such as the interpolation of the staggered grids and reading the subdomain outputs.

3.3.1 Numerical set-up

The simulation was performed using Nyles, a newly created LES code developed by researchers and students at LOPS¹. The model uses an implicit turbulent closure, which consists on representing the subgrid physics relying on its own intrinsic dissipation, i.e. there is no explicit term for the viscous dissipation, instead, the dissipation is done by upwinding the vorticity in the vortex force term, which shows up in the covariant form of the Navier-Stokes equation. The code is still under development but is already fully functional. This simulation was a test for the code and its versatility. This work didn't involve any development or contribution to the mentioned model. The implementation of the plume model was done at a user level.

The simulation has a resolution of $32 \times 64 \times 64$, in a domain of $2000m \times 4000m \times 4000m$ (following the z, y, x convention). The solved variables were buoyancy b , velocity \vec{u} , and pressure p . We solved buoyancy instead of solving for temperature, salinity, and density because it simplifies the computations by condensing the dynamics for all the state variables into one. The domain has fixed boundaries. We set a volumetric buoyancy forcing F_b , as a 3D Gaussian distribution, with a radius of 20 m (1% of L_x). The buoyancy gets injected in a way that the maximum buoyancy is located at the bottom-center of the domain, and it fades with height, spanning just a couple of vertical levels. Horizontally, the buoyancy fades away from the center. We set $F_b = 6.25 \times 10^{-8} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-3}$, which is equivalent to a surface heat flux of $Q = 127 \text{ W m}^{-2}$. We didn't establish an exit velocity to simulate a forced plume exiting a single hydrothermal vent, instead, we assumed that we are simulating a plume at a level in which the rising motion is dominated by buoyancy and not by momentum. The background stratification was set to be linear, with $N^2 = 5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-2}$.

The convection experiments in a stratified environment are known for generating internal gravity waves by the interaction of the buoyant plumes with the upper stratification (Couston et al., 2018). In a box model, the internal waves propagate in the environment and can be reflected by the boundaries, which can cause interference with the flow and with its energy balance. To avoid this scenario, we implemented a sponge layer or nudging in the lateral and top boundaries, in which the velocity and internal waves are damped, avoiding their reflection. Another problem solved with the lateral boundary conditions is that the buoyancy builds up in the domain as time passes, changing the background stratification. This happens because we inject heat in the lower boundary but it never exits the domain. To keep the stratification unchanged, we introduced a buoyancy sink in the lateral boundaries in a way that the cooling balanced the heating done by the source term. In the case with rotation, the buoyancy gets trapped in a

¹Created by Prof. Guillaume Roulet, Markus Reinert, et al. The source code can be found in the following repository: <https://github.com/pvthinker/Nyles>.

vortex that builds-up with time, modifying the plume dynamics and the heat budget. This was the main reason why we didn't include rotation in the experiment.

3.3.2 Control volume determination

The first step towards the implementation of the energy framework was defining a control volume that includes the whole plume in such a way that the flux through the boundaries in the control volume is minimized. We defined this volume as a cylinder, with its center at the source of buoyancy. The radius of the cylinder can go from 0.2 up to 0.4 of the horizontal length L_x , to make sure that the whole plume is contained and to avoid the sponge boundaries. To determine the optimal radius, we computed the lateral mass flux in the cylinder for different radius the mentioned range. We opted for $r = 0.35$ because of the variation of its lateral mass flux similar to $r = 0.4$, the smallest one, and puts the volume farther from the sponge layers. The height of the volume was determined by estimating vertical momentum flux at different levels. The height to the control volume was defined where the momentum flux was 10% of the maximum flux of all levels. On average this level corresponded to a height of 60% of the vertical domain.

3.3.3 Diagnostics

To compute the energy in the reservoirs and their corresponding fluxes, we defined a set of integration methods specifically defined for the cylinder volume. We computed the local quantities that define the fluxes and reservoirs, and we integrated according to its role in the energy framework. In particular, to compute E_a and K we integrate over the volume the local available potential energy and the kinetic energy:

$$E_a = \frac{1}{V} \int_V \frac{(b - b_r(z))^2}{2N_r^2} dV \quad \text{and} \quad K = \frac{1}{2V} \int_V (u^2 + v^2 + w^2) dV, \quad (3.1)$$

where V is the control volume, b is the buoyancy, b_r the background buoyancy, N_r is the background Brunt-Vaisala frequency, and u, v, w are the velocity components.

The same was done for the fluxes, we used their definition described in section 2.3 and we integrated them accordingly to its definition. The fluxes ϕ_z , ϕ_b were integrated over the volume, the flux ϕ_p was integrated only on the top surface of the cylinder, and ϕ_e was integrated on the surface, except for the source of potential energy imposed at the bottom F_b , because we defined it as a volumetric forcing.

To compute the mixing efficiency ε , the plume needs to reach its equilibrium state with the environment, in which the energy content of K and E_a remains practically constant through time. We cannot compute ε using the dissipation terms ϵ_k and ϵ_a , because we cannot directly estimate these terms from the simulation. Instead, we used the equation 2.4, in which we can estimate ϕ_z , ϕ_b , and ϕ_p .

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Analysis of the Mooring time series

In this section, we show the results obtained from the analysis done with the mooring data.

4.1.1 Speed and directional distributions

The average speed per direction and probability density function (PDF) of the direction recorded by the AquaDopp is shown in Figure 4.1. The black curve represents the average speed in each direction, the gray area is its standard deviation, and the red curve is the directional PDF of the speed. The directions in the x -axis are in radians, in which the 0 corresponds to the East, $\pi/2$ to the North, π is the West, and $3\pi/2$ is the South direction. In this figure, we can see how the distributions in 2011 and 2012 differ from the distributions from 2014 to 2019. In 2011 and 2012, we see that the average speed per direction doesn't present any significant peaks indicating a direction where the speed is strongest. Instead, the speed remains constant at around 0.1 m s^{-1} in all directions, with an associated standard deviation of approximately 10% of the mean value. The distribution in 2011, is mainly unimodal, with the largest mode between $\pi/2$ and π , i.e. in the Northwest direction. For 2012, the PDF is bimodal, and the main mode is in Southwest direction. The slow speed and the predominant direction may be due to the position of the instrument. In 2011, the mooring was placed close to the southeast flank of the volcano, close to the trough between the South and West peaks (see Figure 3.1). While in 2012, the mooring was placed in a small canyon, next to the southeast flank, that runs from North to South (see Figure 3.1). This may explain the predominance of the Northwestward direction in 2011 and the Southwestward direction in 2012.

For the years 2014 to 2019 in Figure 4.1, we see that the directional PDFs are mainly bimodal, with predominant modes in the North and South direction. This symmetry in the peaks suggests that the circulation follows an oscillatory pattern. The location of the mooring at these years was further away from the volcano exposing it to the local

Figure 4.1: The average speed in each direction (black) with its associated standard deviation (gray shadow) and the PDF of the direction of the current (red) for the the years with an AquaDopp installed in the line.

currents. The average speed shows more variation in its mean values per direction than in the first two years. In particular, we see how the strongest mean values are in the Northward and Southward direction. Moreover, the standard deviation is larger than in 2011 and 2012, showing that there is more variation in the magnitude of the currents in these locations.

4.1.2 Horizontal kinetic energy spectrum

As already discussed in the previous section, it is convenient to compute the PSD of a signal to see the different forcings present at this particular location. We calculated this with the speed recorded with the AquaDopp instrument, obtaining the horizontal kinetic energy (HKE) spectra for all years with available data. In Figure 4.2, we see the HKE for all years. In particular, the left figure shows the HKE for 2011 and 2012 and the right panel for 2014 to 2019. We separated the HKE into two groups to facilitate the comparison between the curves. In particular, in 2011 and 2012 the power spectrum

is one order of magnitude smaller than for the following years because the mooring was placed in a deeper region with different topographical features than in the following years. In the right figure, we see that the curves for 2014 to 2019 have similar shapes, with the same frequency peaks for frequencies bigger than 1 count per day (cpd). These peaks correspond to the semi-diurnal tidal components M_2 , M_4 and M_6 , marked at the top of the figures. In the spectral estimates for 2014 to 2019, we see a peak that matches the diurnal tidal component K_1 , which is close to the Coriolis frequency f . In both plots is not possible to identify matching peaks for frequencies smaller than 10^{-1} cpd, mainly because the time series were not long enough to record periodic events larger than several weeks.

Figure 4.2: Comparison between the kinetic energy spectra for the different years of the campaign. The comparison was separated into two figures, the left panel for 2011 and 2012, and the right one for 2014 to 2019. The characteristic frequencies are shown at the top x -axis for both figures. At the top margin, the characteristic frequencies in this particular location are shown. f is the Coriolis parameter, M_2 , M_4 and M_6 are the semi-diurnal tidal components, and N is the Brunt-Vaisala frequency at 1700 m deep.

To simplify the analysis, we selected the 2012 and 2017 HKE spectrum estimates, based on their similarity with the other years. These estimates are shown in Figure 4.3. We can classify the spectrum in frequency bands according to the type of motions occurring in the different time ranges. The first region corresponds to frequencies smaller than a period of 100 days for 2017 and 40 days for 2012. In this band, both curves display a nearly white flat band. The following band corresponds to the geostrophic eddy range

and it is defined between the period 100 days up to the inertial frequency f , which is the local Coriolis frequency defined as $f = 2\Omega \sin \theta$. In this band, the HKE estimate falls in an approximate power-law σ^{-b} (where σ is the frequency and b is a constant), this band is geostrophically balanced, below the surface boundary layer. The internal waves band is located at frequencies between $f < \sigma < N$ (where N is the Brunt-Vaisala frequency). This band follows as well an approximate power law and is controlled by gravity wave dynamics. Finally, the frequency band $\sigma > N$ is dominated by small scale turbulence that results from the breaking of internal waves.

Figure 4.3: Horizontal kinetic energy (HKE) estimates recorded with the AquaDopp in 2012 (top) and 2017 (bottom). The labels at the top axis indicate the characteristic frequencies, in particular OO_1 and K_1 are the Lunar diurnal tidal components and M_2 , M_4 and M_6 are the semidiurnal components. N is the Brunt-Vaisala frequency at 1700 m deep. The orange and blue lines indicate slopes correspond fit done for the geostrophic eddy band and the inertial wave band respectively. The dotted line with slope $-5/3$ is for comparison.

For both years, we see that both power spectra have clear peaks that correspond to the different tidal constituents, confirming that there is an amplification of the internal tide in the MORs as observed by Vic et al. (2018). In particular, just before the inertial frequency f there are peaks that match the lunar diurnal tidal frequencies K_1 and OO_1 . Separating the geostrophic eddy band with the internal wave band, we see the inertial peak which is larger for 2012. In the internal wave band ($\sigma > f$) we see peaks that correspond to the internal tides. In particular, we see that the largest and broader peak coincides with the principal lunar semidiurnal constituent M_2 . Also, we identify the M_4 and M_6 semidiurnal peaks which contribute less to the HKE. At the higher frequencies, the resolution of the current meter doesn't allow the spectrum to reach the N frequency

where the breaking of the internal waves occurs. For both bands, the slope of the estimated power-law is -1.02 for 2012 and -1.12 for 2017. The slopes in the internal wave band are -0.75 for 2012 and -0.74 for 2017, which are similar to the -0.81 slope reported by Ferrari and Wunsch (2009) and Fu et al. (1982) at 1500 m deep, 27°N in the MAR. The HKE from both years are similar in their estimated power laws, despite their slightly different topographical placing, suggesting that there is no variation between years.

4.1.3 Temperature power spectral density estimates

Following the same method used to compute the HKE, we calculated the power spectral estimates from the temperature sensors in the mooring. These sensors were predominant in the line throughout all years, making the temperature PSD estimates plots very numerous to display all in this section. Therefore, we show in Figure 4.4 and 4.5 an annual comparison between two RBR sensors at two depths for all the years available and two SBE sensors at different depths for all years. Then from these plots, we select a representative year and we focus our analysis on it. The PSD estimates for the rest of the years can be found in the Appendix A.2.

Figure 4.4: Temperature power spectrum estimate from the RBR at -800 m (top) and at -1580 m (bottom).

As already mentioned, in Figure 4.4 we see the temperature PSD estimate at 800 m

deep (top) and at 1580 m deep (bottom). In the PSD for the 800 m measurements we show only the years from 2014 to 2019, the first three years of the mission there wasn't an RBR installed at that depth. In general, we see how the PSDs for all years are similar between them, especially in the inertial frequency band ($f < \sigma < N$). In this band we see the semidiurnal tidal peak M_2 as predominant, then we see the M_4 with a smaller value, following an approximately power law. Just in the middle of the inertial band, we see a broad peak, corresponding to a frequency of 38 cpd that appears to mark the transition between one power law to another, this will be analyzed more closely further in this section. In the frequency band $\sigma < f$ we see that the power spectrum follows a power law and the curves differ slightly from one another, due to the length of the time series. For the PSD at -1580 m in the bottom panel, we see a similar case where the inertial band is dominated by the internal tide peaks but without the peak at 38 cpd. In general, there is no annual variability in the power spectrum for the temperature.

Figure 4.5: Temperature power spectrum estimate from SBE at -1000 m (top) and at -1690 m (bottom).

In Figure 4.5 we show the power spectral density estimates for the temperature computed from the SBEs installed at -1000 m (top) and at -1690 m (bottom). Compared with the estimates from the RBR, these don't display frequencies higher than N , because of the larger sampling period of the SBEs. In the inertial band, the dominant peak corresponds to the M_2 peak, then followed by the M_4 and M_6 peak. In this region,

the PSD appears to follow a power law. In the frequency band $\sigma < f$, the curves differ slightly from one another, but they display the same decreasing slope. As well as in Figure 4.4, the PSD estimates from the different years are similar between them, and the PSD estimates at -1000 m show the peak at 38 cpd, being especially sharp for 2015. Similar to the RBRs, the SBE spectra are closely similar for all years, at the two depths, again suggesting that there is no variability between the different time series.

Figure 4.6: Temperature power spectral density recorded with the RBR in 2018. The top panel show the PSD from the time series recorded at -800 m down to the one at -1660 m. The lower panel is a zoom of of the top panel between 1 cpd to 10^1 cpd. Both plots mark the characteristic frequencies in the top axis.

From the previous analysis, we selected the 2018 measurements, recorded with an RBR, as a representative year for the temperature, because it had the largest number of sensors per depth installed in the line and it displayed a similar PSD from other years at the same levels. For this year, we estimated the PSD for all depths, which can be seen in Figure 4.6. At the top figure, we see how the different colors represent the PSD from different temperatures, and we note that the power of the signal decreases as the depth increases. In the geostrophic eddy band ($\sigma < f$), we see how the power spectra are larger for the shallower instruments such as -800 m to 1300 m, between 10^{-1} cpd to 1 cpd, this might be due to the presence of mesoscale eddies, which structure can reach these depths. In the inertial band, we see that the spectrum is dominated by the M_2 peak within the order of 10^{-2} °C²/cpd, followed by the M_4 and M_6 peaks, decreasing

in power as frequency increases. The N_{min} and N_{max} are the Brunt-Vaisala frequencies for the bottom depth (-1600 m) and the top depth (-800 m) respectively. Between these two frequencies, we don't see the signature of wave breaking, instead, we see a continuous decaying of the spectrum and a convergence of all the PSDs. Although, in the frequency range 10^1 cpd to 10^2 cpd, we see the broad peak at 38 cpd for depths of 800 m, 900 m and 1200 m, being smoothed as the depth increases. In the bottom panel of Figure 4.6, we see a zoom at the lower spectrum of the inertial frequency band. Between the semidiurnal peaks, we see that the PSD estimates have a higher value for the shallower measurements than for the deeper ones, this is due to the friction from the seafloor that slows the water movements. Also, there is no inertial peak at $\sigma \sim f$ and the lunar diurnal peaks are also not present.

After comparing the temperature and HKE at all depths and at all years (see appendix A.2), and seeing that the PSDs are similar between them, we question the value of having more than 9 years of mooring data in the location. We don't see how another mooring deployment in the same location can give us new information that we don't already have.

4.1.4 Temperature vs. depth distributions

Figure 4.7: Temperature vs. Depth distributions for 2019. The dashed line is the mean temperature profile and each black dot represents the depth of an instrument. At each depth, we have the PDF of the temperature.

As part of the exploration of the temperature time series, we compared the temperature PDF at each depth in the mooring. In Figure 4.7, we show this comparison for the year 2019. The figure shows the distribution in temperature placed at the correspond-

ing depth of the instrument. The dotted line shows the mean profile of temperature vs. depth, where the black dots are the mean temperatures from each instrument. In the PDF we can distinguish between the PDF found at close to the seafloor up to -1300 m above, and the PDF from -1200 m to -800 m. The bottom distributions are approximately Gaussian with a small tail at the right. The shape of these distributions is mainly due to the small variation of the temperature at the bottom, not presenting any other principal mode of variation, meanwhile, the upper distributions show a less defined shape. In particular, we see how the upper ones exhibit a significant amount of anomalies at the right of the principal mode. This could be due to warm mesoscale eddies that pass through the region, such as meddies, which have an anomaly warm and salty core that can extend vertically from around 600 m to 1700 m and can have diameters of around 100 km (Richardson et al., 2000).

4.1.5 Comparison with the ROMS model and the mooring time series

As part of the analysis done with the mooring data, we did a comparison with a virtual mooring taken from a simulation from the North Atlantic done with the Regional Ocean Modeling System (ROMS). This allowed us to compare the quality of the prediction from the model by comparing how the different processes are being solved numerically.

The virtual mooring consists of extracting the time series of the variables of interest for all the vertical levels resolved, in a particular location. In this way, we extracted the data from the grid cell that correspond to the Lucky Strike position and extracted the time series for depth, temperature, and the horizontal components of velocity, to compute the temperature PSD and the HKE estimates of the model. In the following subsection, we compare the model's PSDs with those computed from the mooring from 2019, at four different depths.

Horizontal kinetic energy

In Figure 4.8, we show the comparison between the HKE from the AquaDopp of 2019 and the model output at -1700 m. The black curve corresponds to the HKE from the model and the orange from the mooring. In general, we can note that the model overestimates the HKE, in both the inertial band and in the geostrophic band. We see that for $f \sim 1$ cpd the mooring has a two-crested peak that matches with the lunar diurnal tidal components K_1 and OO_1 , while the model under resolves these peaks, just showing a less prominent one. In the inertial frequency band, we see that the model has a wider M_2 peak, and overestimates the M_4 peak. In the geostrophic band, we see how the model over estimates the HKE almost by an order of magnitude, indicating that

Figure 4.8: Horizontal kinetic energy estimates comparison between the mooring AquaDopp (orange line) and the ROMS model (black line).

Figure 4.9: Comparison of the temperature PSD from the ROMS model (black line) and the mooring PSD (color lines), at -800 m, -1200 m, -1540 m, and -1670 m, respectively.

the model is not accurate matching the HKE spectrum close to the bottom. The main reason of this is that the bathymetry is not represented in high resolution in the model and the seafloor lies ~ 50 m below its actual depth, which causes that the model don't take into account the boundary layer effects.

Temperature

The temperature comparisons are shown in the Figure 4.9, in which we compare the temperature PSD at -800 m, -1200 m, -1540 m, and -1670 m. We see that the model replicates with good accuracy the power spectra at -800 m, -1200 m, and -1540 m, with the semidiurnal tidal peak well defined, compared with the observations. On the other hand, for the PSD at -1670 m, we can see how the model overestimates the motions

for all the spectrum, due to the seafloor representation problem explained before. In general, the model is consistent with the observations and replicates the internal tides measured in the MAR, although there is a slight over estimation at the bottom levels, but this doesn't represent a big problem if the motions in rest of the water column are well represented.

4.2 Plume experiment

We integrated the plume for a time equivalent to 10 days, to let the plume reach its steady-state. In Figure 4.10 we show a snapshot of the plume in its stable state, reached after four days of simulated time. The height of the plume is ~ 1000 m, the height where the vertical velocity vanishes. In the top view plots (center and left), particularly the horizontal transversal section at $z = 0.17 L_z$, we see how the radial velocity of the plume is mainly positive, confirming that the plume extends radially as it goes up. At the top of the control volume $z = 0.6 L_z$, we no longer see the plume structure, instead, we see that the radial velocity oscillates around zero indicating the presence of internal waves generated by the plume bellow. The plume structure remains practically the same for the following days, only changing slightly because of turbulence.

Figure 4.10: Snapshot of the plume at day 5, in its stable state. At the left, we show the vertical velocity w in a vertical cut of the domain done at $y/L_y = 0$. The black dotted lines indicate the limits of the control volume. At the center, the radial component of velocity in a transversal section at $z = 0.17 L_z$ indicated as the orange line in the left panel. At the right the radial velocity at $z = 0.6 L_z$, the top of the control volume.

We computed E_a and K for all the duration of the simulation, to determine the time from which the plume becomes stable. In Figure 4.11, at the left panel, we display the curves that correspond to the energy per unit of volume of both reservoirs. We see that K reaches an stable equilibrium after one day of simulation, oscillating around

a mean value of $1.1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-2}$, with a corresponding standard deviation (STD) of $1.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-2}$. For the E_a we see that the energy builds up until the 4th day, when the trend changes and E_a oscillates around a mean value of $7.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-2}$ with an STD of $6.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-2}$. The long transient state of E_a is due to the small buoyancy fluctuations that build-up at the start of the simulation until the sponge layers can compensate more effectively for this accumulation. The stabilization of E_a was our criterion for establishing the time at which the stable state was reached. To assure that the energy framework is adequate for our experiment, we computed to surface flux of K and E_a . We found that the surface flux of K is practically zero for all time and the surface flux of E_a on average is zero. Therefore, we can assume that the framework defined for the plume holds.

Figure 4.11: On the left, the available potential energy E_a reservoir and the kinetic energy reservoir K , for all time. The blue dotted lines in both plots indicate the start of the stable state of the plume. On the right, the estimates of the energy fluxes ϕ_p , ϕ_b , and ϕ_z .

On the right panel in Figure 4.11, we show the comparison between the total flux ϕ_p , ϕ_b , and ϕ_z . ϕ_b is the energy that is being transformed from the background potential energy E_b to APE, per unit of time. This flux has a mean value of $2 \times 10^4 \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-3}$ and it quantifies the conversion that takes place inside all the control volume. The APE of the system gets converted to K , by the ϕ_z flux with a mean value of $4.1 \times 10^3 \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-3}$. From the kinetic energy, almost all of it is radiated to the wave field via the term ϕ_p with an average value of $2.5 \times 10^3 \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-3}$. This suggests that 60% of the newly created kinetic energy gets irradiated to the internal wave field, and the 40% remaining is dissipated by ϵ_k , which has an average value of $1.6 \times 10^3 \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-3}$ (recalling that the flux of kinetic energy through the boundaries of the control volume is zero).

By determining the ϕ_p , ϕ_b , and ϕ_z fluxes, we were able to estimate the mixing efficiency of the plume, by using equation 2.4. Figure 4.12 shows the mixing efficiency at all times of the simulation. Discarding the first four days, the mean mixing efficiency was estimated to be ~ 0.7 . This is much larger than the 0.2 mixing efficiency assumed in the ocean. The main reason for this is that in the plume the turbulence is driven by

Figure 4.12: Estimated mixing efficiency of the plume at all times, and its corresponding average in red.

buoyancy, whereas in the ocean the turbulence is driven by shear.

As a final remark, in our analysis we omitted the computation of the background potential energy because this reservoir depends on the definition of the origin in the z -axis, and is a huge reservoir compared with K and E_a .

5 Conclusion

The observations from the mooring gave us an insight into the main processes occurring over Lucky Strike. From the power spectral estimates, we can conclude that this region is dominated by internal tides, showing dominant peaks that match the frequencies of the diurnal and semidiurnal tidal components. This result explains the bimodal directional distributions recorded by the current meter placed at the bottom, where the current oscillates between two main directions, North and South. These directions depend on the local bathymetry and the position of the instrument, as shown in the current distributions for 2011 and 2012.

In the HKE estimates of the mooring, we showed that the measurements are similar to other HKE estimates done at the MAR at the same depth, indicating that the processes happening in Lucky Strike are characteristic of other MAR sites. In the temperature power spectra, we showed that the estimates for the 9 years are closely similar between them, not displaying big changes in their spectrum. These results suggest that there is no more interest in placing the mooring in the same location for another year and could be more interesting to place it closer to the vent field to observe the hydrothermal vents plume. Also, in the temperature PSD, there was the consistent appearance of the peak at 38 cpd, between -800 m to -1300 m. What is causing this peak to appear in the spectrum remains unidentified and could be explored in the following campaigns by placing a couple of current meter at these levels, or using other measuring methods, to get more information about the process that might be causing this peak. For the proper detection of passing eddies thorough the mooring, it is necessary to increase the spatial resolution of the current meters, by placing them in the upper and middle part of the line, this would give us more information of the water column that can help us to identify the structure of the eddies.

Regarding the plume experiment, the energy framework that we derived for the plume, proved to be efficient in computing the flux terms that supply and dissipate the kinetic energy and available potential energy in the system. The definition of this framework based in an open control volume assumes a more realistic scenario, because not always is possible to assume a closed system for analyzing certain processes happening in nature, especially those that occur in the ocean. The computed mixing efficiency of the

plume had a reasonable value of 0.7, but we couldn't compare it with other experiments done in plume mixing efficiency. The comparison of this quantity with other numerical or laboratory experiments remains a task for the future. Another future objective is to increase the resolution of the simulation and redo the energy analysis, to see if there is a significant change in our energy estimates and mixing efficiency. In our relative low resolution experiment, we see that the the turbulence is pretty well represented, so we don't expect very different results to the ones presented in this work.

Another task that remains open to explore is the inclusion of rotation in the experiment. It can be interesting if it is possible to implement this framework with rotation (changing certain aspects such as the horizontal domain size) and if it gives a different result regarding the energy budget and the mixing efficiency.

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A Appendix

A.1 Derivation of the mechanical energy budget

Two expressions for the APE density can be contemplated: the exact one associated with the Boussinesq equations

$$e_{a1}(b; z) = - \int_{z_r(b)}^z (b - b_r(z')) dz', \quad (\text{A.1})$$

or the quadratic one associated with the quasi-geostrophic equations

$$e_{a2}(b; z) = \frac{(b - b_r(z))^2}{2N_r(z)^2}. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

In the limit of small fluctuations, or in the special case of a linear stratification ($N_r(z)$ is constant) then the two expressions are identical. In our experiments we have N_r constant, therefore $z_r(b) - z = N_r^{-2}(b - b_r(z))$ also holds.

The local budget is formed by taking the material derivative of e_a , then using $D_t z = w$ and $D_t b = F_b$, we have

$$D_t e_a = -w(b - b_r(z)) - F_b(z - z_r(b)). \quad (\text{A.3})$$

The two terms on the r.h.s. are respectively the potential to kinetic conversion term (ϕ_z in the volume integrated budget) and the conversion from the background to the available potential energy due to the forcing ($-\phi_{b2}$ in the integrated budget). Note that because the turbulent closure is done implicitly by the discretization of the advection terms, the mixing term does not show up, it is hidden in the $\nabla(\mathbf{u}e_a)$ on the l.h.s.. We define the background energy density e_b as a remainder $e_b = e_p - e_a$, with $e_p = -bz$ the potential energy density. We thus have

$$D_t e_b = -wb_r(z) - F_b z_r(b). \quad (\text{A.4})$$

The integrated budget is obtained by integrating (A.3) and (A.4) over the control volume. For the APE, $E_a = \int_V e_a dV$, the control volume is chosen large enough so that e_a vanishes along the boundaries. Therefore

$$\partial_t E_a = -\phi_z + \phi_{b2} - \epsilon_a \quad (\text{A.5})$$

where ϵ_a is the net dissipation of APE induced by the upwinding of the advection term. For the background potential energy, $E_b = \int_V e_b dV$, there is an exchange term through the boundaries, as $e_b = -b_r(z)z$ along the boundaries. Therefore

$$\partial_t E_b = \int_V \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u} b_r(z) z) dV - \int_V w b_r(z) dV - \int_V F_b z dV - \phi_{b2} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

The second term can be turned into a flux term by introducing $\partial_z p_r = -b_r$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_V w b_r(z) dV &= - \int_V w \partial_z p_r dV \\ &= - \int_{S_{top}} w p_r dS + \int_{S_{bot}} w p_r dS + \int_V p_r \partial_z w dV \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

The two first terms of the r.h.s. vanish because there is no net vertical flux through the control volume. The third term can be transformed into an horizontal flux with $\partial_z w = -\nabla_h \mathbf{u}_h$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_V p_r \partial_z w dV &= - \int_{\partial V} \mathbf{u}_h \cdot \mathbf{n} p_r dS \\ &= - \int_{\partial V} \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n} p_r dS \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

where we have used the property that there is no vertical flux through the boundaries. To summarize, the net flux of background potential energy into the control volume is

$$\phi_E = \int_V \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u} b_r(z) z - p_r(z)) dV - \int_V F_b z dV \quad (\text{A.9})$$

and

$$\partial_t E_b = -\phi_b + \phi_3 + \epsilon_a \quad (\text{A.10})$$

Note that ϵ_a comes in because there is no dissipation of E_p .

A.2 Temperature power spectral density estimates

Figure A.1: Temperature power spectral density recorded with the RBR from 2011 to 2019, except 2018 that is shown in Figure 4.6. The top axis labels mark the characteristic frequencies. N_{max} is the maximum and N_{min} is the minimum Brunt-Vaisala frequencies between depth range of the instruments; f is the Coriolis frequency; M_2 , M_4 , and M_6 are the semidiurnal tidal frequencies.

Figure A.2: Temperature power spectral density recorded with the SBE from 2011 to 2019. The top axis labels mark the characteristic frequencies. N_{max} is the maximum and N_{min} is the minimum Brunt-Vaisala frequencies between depth range of the instruments; f is the Coriolis frequency; M_2 , M_4 , and M_6 are the semidiurnal tidal frequencies.